

Quantum information processing in a neuron: a proposal

Aman Chawla *Member, IEEE*, and Salvatore D Morgera, *Life Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—It was recently argued that a neuron would decohere very rapidly from any quantum superposition of its “on” and “off” states. We argue that a hot, wet, biological device such as a neuron is not a two state device but is better modeled as a “quasi-analog” device with a very large number of basis states. Under this model, the neuron is shown to have a decoherence time which is on the order of 1 millisecond, the timescale of an action potential. This would imply that quantum information may be stored and processed by a neuron.

Index Terms—quantum decoherence, analog, neuron, qudit, coherence, human brain.

I. INTRODUCTION

They are long-standing, open questions having to do with the human brain such as, “Is the brain analog or digital?” and “What is the real model of computation in the brain?” [4]. Some researchers have argued that since the brain exhibits the marvelous phenomenon of consciousness, there must be some equally marvelous and exotic quantum mechanism underlying the brain’s activity [5]. Other researchers have argued that hot, wet biological tissue cannot sustain quantum coherence sufficiently long for quantum computation to be a viable model for information processing in the brain [7]. In this work, we do not pretend to answer these long-standing questions but do reinforce the possibility that the most fundamental element of the human nervous system, the nerve fiber, performs quantum information processing.

II. REVIEW OF TEGMARK’S RESULT

In neurophysiology an axon is sub-divided into myelinated internodal segments and nodes of Ranvier. The nodes are dense in ion channels (please see Fig. 1). In the paper by Tegmark, the node of Ranvier of a myelinated nerve fiber is treated as being in a superposition of on and off states where on refers to ‘there is a spike’ and off refers to ‘there is no spike’ [7]. This approach is based on the view that the action potential modality of neural information processing is a binary modality. In this view, no recognition is given to the fact that concomitant with any transmembrane current flow, there would be an electric field generated under the biological quasistatic electrostatics assumption [6], [1].

Tegmark considers ion-ion collisions and ion-water collisions as being among the few mechanisms that would lead to decoherence in the superposition of ions inside and ions

outside a node of Ranvier, separated by the thickness of the cell membrane. He finds, in both settings, the decoherence time to be about 10^{-20} seconds which is much shorter than the 1 millisecond time period of an action potential. Based on this calculation, he then argues in favor of the critics of the quantum proposal and concludes that there is no need to hypothesize quantum computation in the brain.

Our view is quite different and is based on the importance of electric near-fields generated concomitantly with the action potential [1], [9]. We believe that understanding these electric near-fields and their role in information processing and communication in nervous tissue is crucial for understanding the complexity of brain information processing. In the next section we show how quantum information processing can occur in a neuron.

III. THE MODEL

Consider the fact that when a voltage gated sodium ion channel opens, the sodium current rises from zero to about 2 pA, stays at roughly 2 pA and within a short duration (about 0.5 ms) of time, falls back down to zero. The zero current flow state is left only when there is an ambient depolarization step applied to the ion channel under patch-clamp measurement conditions (please see Fig. 2). Probabilistic summation of many such sodium ion channel “pulses” leads to the macroscopically visible, characteristic sodium channel current shape that is recorded by electrophysiologists.

Concomitant with such a current pulse, there will be an electric field generated. A study of such electric fields was made in [2], [1], [3]. These electric fields are real-valued entities - the field strength is a real number. In our view, the ultrastructure of these fields encodes vital information about the presence and strength of ion channel currents, and cannot be ignored. Taking our cue from this importance of ultrastructure, we propose that instead of a two-level quantum system, we model the neuron as an L -level quantum system, where L can be a very large number, to adequately make use of the fine structure of the field, which originates in the fine structure of the current flowing in the ion channels.

In the next section we look at precisely this ultrastructure in the ion channel current profile, set up a quantum system and extend Tegmark’s decoherence computation to this system.

A. Chawla is with the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, India. e-mail: ac274@cornell.edu.

S.D.Morgera is with the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of South Florida, Tampa, FL 33620, USA. e-mail: sdmorgera@usf.edu.

Fig. 1. Schematic showing an axon in side and cross-sectional views. Also shown are the node of Ranvier and a zoomed in view of a single ion channel. In the single ion channel view, we show a snapshot of the possibilities that might occur within a window of ΔT seconds. A few of them are shown. The ion could have not moved at all, or moved the entire h meters distance, or some intermediate distance. These would all correspond to different currents and hence distinct electric field states.

Fig. 2. Schematic showing single Na^+ ion channel patch clamp recording (middle trace). The channel conducts a peak of 2 pA current when a voltage step of +80 mV is applied (top trace). Adapted from Fig. 3 of [8].

IV. THE DECOHERENCE COMPUTATION

For the case of ion-ion collisions, Tegmark derives the following time evolution function f

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(x, x', t) &= e^{-\Lambda t(1 - e^{-|x' - x|^2/(2\lambda^2)})} \\
 &\approx e^{-|x' - x|^2 \Lambda t / (2\lambda^2)} \text{ for } |x' - x| \ll \lambda, \\
 &\approx e^{-\Lambda t} \text{ for } |x' - x| \gg \lambda.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In the subsequent computation he uses the fact that while the deBroglie wavelength of a sodium ion or a water molecule is about 0.03 nm, the spatial separation between the ions on the inside and those on the outside (i.e. the ions occupying the two distinct states) would be about the thickness of the cell membrane, or about $h = 10\text{nm}$. Given that the latter value is much larger than the former value of 0.03 nm, he immediately ignores the case $|x' - x| \ll \lambda$.

However, if we look at the ion current in the ion channel and divide it into L levels, with the first level being that the ion flows the distance from 0 (inside) to h (outside) in ΔT

seconds, the second level being that the ion flows the distance from 0 to $h - h/L$ in ΔT seconds and so on, until the k th level is the ion flowing the distance from 0 to $h - k * h/L$ in ΔT seconds, then, modeling each level as a basis state leads to currents as small as charge $\times h/(L * \Delta T)$ being important.

When we are looking at a ΔT snapshot in the ion channel, in one case the ion would have covered h/L distance and in the second case perhaps $6h/L$ distance. Both of these correspond to different currents. Thus the two (positional) states are separated by $5h/L$ distance units. The single-particle density matrix ρ of Tegmark's section B.1 would therefore evolve following the second case of $|x' - x| \ll \lambda$. This is because quantum coherence now needs to be maintained over only a distance of $5h/L$, and taking L to be suitably large, we can have the LHS be smaller than 0.03 nm.

If we plug in L to be about $8e10$, we find the decoherence time to be about 1 millisecond, which is the typical action potential time scale.

V. LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this computation, we didn't include ion-water collisions as well as interactions with distant ions.

To conclude, if we take the neuron and analyze it at the ion channel level where tiny currents are flowing, then those currents can be basis states for the formation of qudits, with d or L being very large. In such a case, quantum coherent information could be generated at the ion channel, stay coherent for the duration of an action potential, whence, via the e-field it can be broadcast to other nodes on distant axons.

Ion channel states on neighboring ion channels can also be entangled with each other via the field generated and the common depolarization applied to the entire node. This study and its consequences for quantum information processing in the neuron is left for future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aman Chawla. On axon-axon interaction via currents and fields. 2017.
- [2] Aman Chawla, Salvatore Morgera, and Arthur Snider. Field theory of axon interaction. *To be submitted to IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 2019.
- [3] Colin G Hales and Susan Pockett. The relationship between local field potentials (lfps) and the electromagnetic fields that give rise to them. *Frontiers in systems neuroscience*, 8:233, 2014.
- [4] Christof Koch. *Biophysics of computation: information processing in single neurons*. Oxford university press, 2004.
- [5] Roger Penrose. *Shadows of the Mind*, volume 4. Oxford University Press Oxford, 1994.
- [6] Robert Plonsey and Dennis B Heppner. Considerations of quasi-stationarity in electrophysiological systems. *The Bulletin of mathematical biophysics*, 29(4):657–664, 1967.
- [7] Max Tegmark. Importance of quantum decoherence in brain processes. *Physical review E*, 61(4):4194, 2000.
- [8] Peter Vassilev, Todd Scheuer, and William A Catterall. Inhibition of inactivation of single sodium channels by a site-directed antibody. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 86(20):8147–8151, 1989.
- [9] Andrea Zangari, Davide Micheli, Roberta Galeazzi, and Antonio Tozzi. Node of ranvier as an array of bio-nanoantennas for infrared communication in nerve tissue. *Scientific reports*, 8(1):539, 2018.